

B. Use of semidwarf parents in Indian rice breeding programs over a 10-year period. Three hundred parents used in 140 randomly selected crosses at 7 agricultural experiment stations and universities, India.

C. Use of semidwarf parents in rice breeding programs of 6 Asian nations (excluding India) over a 10-year period. Five hundred and nineteen parents used in 215 randomly selected crosses at 7 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 6 Asian nations, 1965-75.

semidwarfs – from almost zero to use in almost half of the crosses in 10 years. Most of such semidwarfs were progeny of earlier crosses with TN1 or IR8.

Because more than a third of the crosses analyzed were made at seven research centers in India, the data were analyzed to determine if Indian rice

breeders differed from fellow rice breeders in the six other nations in the adoption of genetic materials.

By 1974–75, 75% of the crosses made in the Indian sample involved a locally developed semidwarf; 21% involved an IRRI parent other than IR8; and 7%, a semidwarf introduced from another

country (figure, B). In the six other countries, IRRI was the major source of semidwarf parents (figure, C). But the same strong trend toward the use of locally developed semidwarfs was found.

The 111 times that a semidwarf variety was used as a parent in 1974–75 involved 83 separate varieties or breeding lines.

Ancestry of locally developed semidwarf rices used as parents in Asian rice breeding programs in 1974–75

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In a study of the diffusion of genetic materials among rice breeding programs in different countries of Asia, almost half of the 377 randomly selected crosses made in 1974–75 at 14 agricultural experiment stations in 7 Asian nations involved the use of at least one *locally developed* parent. The sources of the semidwarf gene were determined by analyzing the ancestry of the local semidwarfs. Genes were traced back two or three generations.

Seventy-six percent of the local semidwarf parents were progeny of IR8 or other IRRI varieties and lines (see figure, A). For example, the variety K35, used as a parent in India, is a progeny of the cross IR8/HR19; RD1, used in Thailand, is from Leuang Tawng/IR8.

Twenty-four percent of the local

semidwarfs such as Sona (TN1/GEB 24) and Jaya (TN1/T141) were progeny of TN1. Twenty-five percent of the rices had at least two different semidwarf parents; for example Tong-il, often used in Korean crosses, is from the cross IR8//Yukara/TN1.

But a fourth of the local semidwarf parents were themselves progenies of local semidwarfs that had been developed earlier. The genetic composition of those second-generation ancestors was determined next. Eighty percent were found to be progeny of TN1 (figure, B), Thirty-three percent had both TN1 and IR8 in their ancestry. For example, Pusa 33, used in three crosses, is a progeny of a cross of Ratna (TKM 6/IR8) with Improved Sabarmati (TN1*3/Basmati 370).

Because TN1, IR8, and most other semidwarfs have Dee-geo-woo-gen (DGWG) as a common ancestor, the DGWG gene may be assumed to be in about 80% of the crosses analyzed for 1974–75.

A. Source of semidwarf gene in 59 locally developed semidwarf rices used as parents in 1974–75 crosses. B. Source of semidwarf gene in the ancestors of local semidwarfs that were used as parents in 1974–75 crosses.

Thus, although by the mid-1970's the original stiff-strawed varieties such as TN1 and IR8 were virtually phased out

of breeding programs as direct parents, almost all the semidwarf parents that replaced them were their progeny.

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Invitation to participate in an international rice genetic survey

The increasing volume of hybridizations made in national and international rice improvement programs and the accelerated exchange of genetic material necessitate the establishment of a permanent and comprehensive record bank for the use of present and future generations of rice scientists. Some hybridization records from early breeding programs have been lost; others are relatively inaccessible. The record bank could provide information on any rice variety, including its complete genetic ancestry and the extent of its use in farmers' fields or in crosses.

Such information can help scientists to identify possible sources of resistance and to avoid the inherent dangers of genetic uniformity in the world's rice crop. IRRI invites rice scientists to collaborate in an *international rice genetic survey* to systematically gather, store, and disseminate such information. The information will be made available to all rice researchers and will help IRRI scientists and collaborators from national programs focus on problem areas considered most critical.

Information on rice varieties most widely grown by farmers, on the newest varieties released by national programs, and on elite breeding lines is also needed.

By analyzing the genetic background and traits of elite breeding lines in various programs - and of parent materials used in crosses - scientists can anticipate the types of varieties that would be released within the next few years.

We request that each breeding program send to IRRI a list of the varieties and lines described (see following) and copies of hybridization records.

MOST WIDELY GROWN VARIETIES, those grown on more than 50,000 ha within a political region or, for smaller areas, the varieties most extensively grown in farmers' fields. Include the following information:

- varietal name (or names, in some cases)
- cross (if of hybrid origin) or progenitor (if pureline selection or mutant)
- origin of variety
- plant height
- state, province, or region (political)
- main season (or seasons) grown
- agroclimatic conditions or type of culture (rainfed lowland, deep water, etc.)
- growth duration (days from seed to seed)
- estimate of the area on which grown (both total number of hectares and percent of total rice land in the state, province, or region)
- major important agronomic traits (gall midge resistance, grain quality, etc.)

NEWEST RICE VARIETIES, released by each station over the past 10 years.

Include the following information:

- varietal name
- source of variety
- previous line designation
- cross (if of hybrid origin) or progenitor (if pureline selection or mutant) from which the variety was selected
- plant height
- growth duration (days from seed to seed)
- agroclimatic conditions or type of culture for which recommended (rainfed lowland, deep water, etc.)
- state, province, or region (political) where released
- estimate of the area on which the variety is grown (both total number of hectares and percent of total rice land in the state, province, or region)
- important agronomic traits

ELITE BREEDING LINES, the most promising prerelease lines in advanced yield trials of the ultimate stage of testing (on-station, regional, minikit, or production trials). Will probably be no more than 10 lines/geographic region.

Please provide information on:

- line designation
- cross from which the line was selected
- plant height
- growth duration
- agroclimatic conditions or type of culture for which intended
- important agronomic traits
- state, province, or region (political)

HYBRIDIZATION OR CROSSING

RECORDS, made since the initiation of crossbreeding at various stations. Anyone who has access to old crossing records from programs that no longer exist is also requested to provide a copy so that the ancestry of varieties that came from those crosses will not be lost to future generations. Include:

- name of station and country
- line designation (K, BR, etc.) and number
- cross (female parent first, then male)
- year (approx.) that cross was made

The information should be sent to:

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Manila, Philippines

Thank you in advance for your time and consideration.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Germplasm conservation

Primitive cultivated rices and wild relatives from the Chhotanagpur region of southern Bihar, India

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The hilly, rainfed Chhotanagpur region of southern Bihar is predominantly